

OCCASIONS AND DEVELOPMENTS OF THE EMERGENCE OF PHARMACY

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Abstract. *The era of primitive society is the longest in the history of mankind. According to Professor Yu. P. Lisitsyn, it lasted hundreds of thousands of children, and the entire history of civilization in comparison is no more than one percent. The history of medicine (and pharmacy E. Elyashevich), starting with the first signs of civilization, the transition from the primitive communal to the slave system, and the formation of cities, dates back only a few thousand years. The state of pharmacy of this period was studied using archaeological methods: during excavations of burials, medicines and labor items were found, which may have been used for grinding medicinal herbs and minerals) objects of art.*

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In the ancient Indian sacred book “Ayur Veda” (Science of Life) there is the following saying: “In the hands of an ignoramus, medicine is poison and, in its action, can be comparable to a knife, fire or light. In the hands of knowledgeable people, it is likened to the drink of immortality”. This idea runs like a red thread through the entire history of pharmacy and the organization of the pharmaceutical business, both in our country and abroad. It defines many of the deontological and ethical positions of the modern pharmacist. And the word “pharmacy” itself comes from the Egyptian word “pharmaki”, which means “the bestower of safety or healing.”

This is also evidenced by the inscription under the image of the Egyptian god of healing art, Thoth. From here, obviously, came the Greek word “pharmakon” - “medicine”, which then passed into all languages of the world.

The term “pharmacist” appears in Ancient Rome, starting in the 3rd century BC. This was the name given to persons involved not only in the preparation of medicines, but also in the treatment of patients. At the same time, the word pharmacology came into use - people involved in the preparation of medicines and the sale of raw medicinal materials. One of the outstanding doctors of Ancient Greece, Hippocrates (461–337 BC) formulated the basic principles of medical ethics that also apply to medicine: “Medicines and their simple properties, if they are described, you must carefully keep in mind.

From them you must learn everything that relates to the treatment of disease in general, and finally, how much and how they act in certain diseases. For this is the beginning, middle and end of the knowledge of medicines”. Modern medical deontology, considering the problems of debt and the activities of medical and pharmaceutical workers, proceeds from the specifics of their work. It covers the social and ethical aspects of responsibility, social significance, vocation, and purpose of the profession.

The same questions worried doctors and pharmacists in ancient times. Hippocrates, in his famous “Oath,” substantiated one of the main professional and moral requirements of medical deontology - to help people strengthen and protect their health, regardless of social and property status, social, national and racial background.

This “Oath” has been the main ethical document in medicine for more than 2 thousand years, and it also became the basis of the oath of pharmacists. Centuries of experience, recorded in the annals of traditional medicine, testify to the keen observation, great ingenuity and remarkable talents of the people.

Traditional medicine is the predecessor of scientific medicine and feeds it with its experience and observations. Modern doctors widely use traditional medicine such as marshmallow root, calamus root, arnica, elderberry, valerian, gentian, adonic, oak bark, elderberry, datura, sweet clover, serpentine, cranberry, viburnum, coriander, buckthorn, lavender, licorice, lily of the valley, linden blossom, flaxseed, raspberry, coltsfoot, almond, rhubarb, chamomile, etc.

The famous ancient Greek physician and thinker Hippocrates attached great importance to medicinal science. He argued that in nature, medicines are already given in a ready-made form, in an optimal state and combination. He used medicines without mixing.

Hippocrates paid special attention to herbal treatment, clearly defining the methods and conditions for their storage. Among the herbal medicines that he used were henbane, elderberry, pomegranate, melon, St. John's wort, centaury, iris, castor bean, hellebore, chilibuha, garlic, sage and others - a total of 230 plants. Of the medicinal products of animal origin, fats were especially popular: for example, sheep fat, ox fat, goose fat, duck fat, and fish oil. Metals and precious stones were used externally.

Hippocrates formulated the basic principles of medical ethics, also related to medicine: “Medicines and their simple properties, if they are described, you must carefully keep in mind. From them you must assimilate everything that relates to the treatment of the disease in general, finally, how much and in what way”. “In this way they act in certain diseases. For this is the beginning, middle and end of the knowledge of medicines”.

The development of ancient Roman medicine is directly related to the activities of the outstanding ancient Roman physician and naturalist Claudius Galen (131-201 AD). He adhered to the following principles: to treat “like with like”, “opposite with opposite”, “help nature”. In accordance with these views, medicines were used, which were divided into three classes: simple, complex, specific.

Galen introduced the concept of active substances, according to which he widely used extracts from natural materials, as well as wines and syrups, in practice. Galen described in his writings the preparation of powders, pills, lozenges, soaps, ointments, and plasters. He had a pharmacy in Rome, where he himself prepared medicines for the sick.

The thousand-year practice of using the most rational healing techniques and the most effective medicines of plant, animal and mineral origin, which arose in the era of the primitive communal system and were passed down orally from generation to generation, is called traditional medicine.

The ability to support a patient morally and spiritually, not to ignore his requests, to take care of every person who turns to a pharmacy for help - this is the high mission of a modern pharmacist.

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